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Bridging The Gap: How EU climate research projects can better support Early-Career Researchers

White Paper

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Executive summary

Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe programmes (especially under Pillar 2 – Global Challenges) encourage the involvement and development of Early-Career Researchers (ECRs). However, current support across projects remains uneven and is not always well tailored to ECRs' needs.

The results of our survey of ECRs in climate and geosciences research communities show that, while some activities are valued across all career stages, such as developing one's own research project and technical skills development, key ECR needs shift with experience: early-stage ECRs tend to prioritise hands-on skill development and mentoring; mid-stage ECRs increasingly seek leadership opportunities and cross-partner exchanges; and experienced ECRs emphasise proposal leadership and career continuity beyond the project.

We recommend that EU projects treat ECR development as a planned project function, embedding (and resourcing) structured mentoring and career support, opportunities for ECR leadership and ownership of outputs, targeted training linked to project tools and methods, regular interaction with senior researchers, mobility/exchanges across partners, and proactive support for transitions. These measures should be designed from the proposal stage, with dedicated resources and regular tracking.

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Contents

01	Introduction: why this white paper?
02	Early-career researchers and the challenges they face
03	Methods: understanding the gap
04	ECR needs and expectations
05	Current landscape of ECR support in EU research projects
06	The gap: disconnect between expectations and opportunities
07	Bridging the gap: recommendations for EU research projects
08	Conclusion: toward meaningful ECR engagement in EU research projects

1. Introduction: Why this white paper?

Early-career researchers (ECRs), including PhD candidates and postdoctoral fellows working in EU research projects, represent the next generation of scientists who will shape the future of the European research landscape and tackle global challenges. Supporting their development is an investment in individual careers and should be considered a strategic priority for the EU research ecosystem. EU-funded research projects — key drivers of research funding and collaboration across countries, institutions, disciplines, and generations — are uniquely positioned to provide ECRs with high-quality training, mentorship, and leadership opportunities. By doing so, they can also help reduce persistent inequalities in ECR support across Europe^{1,2}.

Despite increasing awareness, a significant body of research continues to highlight the need for projects to implement dedicated activities that consistently add value to ECRs' development. Coordination teams frequently cite uncertainty about which activities to propose, limited resources, or a lack of engagement from ECRs themselves. These patterns point to a clear disconnect between the needs and expectations of ECRs and the support currently offered within EU projects. This white paper, focusing on the broader climate and geosciences research communities, aims to examine that gap and provide concrete, actionable solutions that EU research projects can adopt to better support ECRs.

2. Early-career researchers and the challenges they face

A broad definition of early-career researchers is used in this white paper, including a wide range of research-enabling professionals in the early stages of their careers, regardless of age, as defined by Pizzolato et al. (2023)¹ (and with up to 10 years of research experience). This includes PhD students, junior postdoctoral researchers, and early-career professionals outside of academia, such as research engineers, scientists in government bodies and NGOs, consultants and administrators who are involved in funded research activities.

Considering the heterogeneity of this group, we examined the factors that make the greatest difference in responses to a particular question and concluded that experience level is the primary factor. Therefore, the participants were divided into three categories based on their years of research experience: 0-2 years, 3-5 years, and 6+ years.

The challenges facing early-career researchers are well-documented in the literature and are known to many academic and funding institutions. For instance, ECRs often struggle with job insecurity due to short-term contracts and limited funding opportunities, making it difficult to plan long-term careers. This can influence the planning of personal and family lives or affect mental health.

In Nature's survey³ of 7600 postdocs conducted at the end of 2020, 51% of respondents had at some point considered leaving active research due to work-related mental-health concerns, including anxiety and depression⁴.

Additionally, limited mentorship, autonomy, and networking opportunities can hinder ECRs' professional growth and visibility in their fields. As stated by Woolston (2020)⁴, postdocs' positions are often poorly defined between a student and a staff member, making it difficult to receive the recognition, benefits, and support that they deserve.

The pressure to publish, alongside the increasing competition for research grants, can cause stress that may lead to prioritising "quantity over quality". There is often not enough time or opportunity for truly independent research (only 18% of respondents to Nature's survey from 2020 who have their own grants or fellowships reported that they could take their project with them if they changed institutions⁵), which Laudel and Gläser (2008)⁶ see as a result of a "market failure" of the university system.

Some of these challenges are also reflected in the results of the survey conducted within the scope of this white paper that addresses the perspectives of climate and geosciences ECRs.

¹Pizzolato D., Reyes Elizondo A., Aubert Bonn N. et al. (2023) Bridging the gap – how to walk the talk on supporting early career researchers [version 1; peer review: 3 approved]. *Open Res Europe* 2023, 3:75.

²Ivancheva L. & Gourova E. (2011) Challenges for career and mobility of researchers in Europe. *Science and Public Policy*, 38 (3),185–198.

³Nature's 2020 post-doc survey: <https://figshare.com/s/a0a0f1c90843c12e6373>.

⁴Woolston (2020) Postdocs under pressure: 'Can I even do this any more?' *Nature* 587, 689-692.

⁵Woolston (2020) Postdoc survey reveals disenchantment with working life. *Nature* 587, 505-508.

⁶Laudel G. & Gläser J. (2008) From apprentice to colleague: The metamorphosis of Early Career Researchers. *Higher Education*, 55, 387–406.

3. Methods: Understanding the gap

Our methods combined a literature review (non-exhaustive and including grey literature), two online surveys (in 2025), and the practical experience of authors and reviewers, many of whom lead ECR activities in EU projects or are ECRs themselves.

The first online survey targeted ECRs in climate and geosciences fields worldwide, beginning with the networks of the authors and contributors working on European research projects, and ECR well-established groups (e.g., the Young Earth System Scientists community, YESS). Therefore, the majority of the 91 respondents were European, and almost 60% were involved in an ongoing EU-funded research project at the time of responding. It is important to note that ECRs involved in EU-funded projects may be hosted by a wide range of institutions, from universities and research centres to public-sector organisations, NGOs, and private companies, and may be based in different national contexts, all of which can shape their experiences as ECRs. This survey aimed to gather ECRs' experiences and opinions on activities organised to support them, as well as their future needs and interests. Questions included demographic information and current

engagement in ECR initiatives, as well as open-ended questions that gathered their opinions on the most impactful activities and suggestions for the future of ECR support in research projects.

The second online survey mapped ECR-focused initiatives in EU research projects on climate and geosciences topics, covering project context, activities (implemented/planned), perceived success and shortcomings, design aims, preferred formats, development challenges, and impact assessment. This survey was circulated to more than 20 projects and received 13 responses; however, because projects without ECR-focused activities were not explicitly asked to respond, the response rate should be interpreted with caution.

Limitations include non-probability sampling, over-representation of EU-funded respondents, and self-reporting bias; results indicate patterns rather than definitive prevalence.

4. ECR needs and expectations

Perceived value of existing initiatives

This subsection focuses on mapping and understanding the current availability of ECR-focused initiatives and their perceived value.

Among the ECRs who responded to the survey, conference sessions (69.7%), webinars (55.1%), and summer schools (51.7%) were the most attended activities, followed by social events (47.2%), networking sessions (38.2%), and career development workshops (33.7%), while mentoring programs (21.3%) and hackathons (13.5%) were the least frequently attended. One respondent added that they also attended college training on different topics with the possibility to talk, share, and listen to the experiences of other ECRs, as well as PhD days organised by their laboratory, mentioning a mix of these types of activities in one event. Overall, academic and knowledge-sharing events had higher attendance than skill-building or mentoring activities in the surveyed group. However, these figures reflect attendance only and do not distinguish between lack of interest, lack of availability, or lack of access to such activities.

The ECRs were also asked to rank on a scale of 1 ('Not valuable at all') to 5 ('Very valuable') the value of various activities they have attended (Fig. 1). As different respondents attended different types of activities, there may be biases in their value rankings. Across all experience levels (0–2 years, 3–5 years, and 6+ years), summer schools, conferences, mentoring, and networking were generally the most valued (ratings 4–5). Hackathons tend to be rated lower, particularly by researchers with 6+ years of experience, while less experienced researchers (0–2 years) view them more positively. Overall, as researchers gain more experience, they place greater value on mentoring, networking, and career development, while activities such as webinars and hackathons become less important. This may reflect a greater prioritisation of hard or technical skills development during earlier years, shifting subsequently to prioritise development of their careers and visibility to create opportunities for the future.

How ECRs of different career stages ranked project activities beyond research.

Figure 1 | Value rankings of attended activities for each experience-level group. Note: Rating 1 = 'Not valuable at all', and Rating 5 = 'Very valuable'.

Priorities for future support

To assess the priorities for future support, survey participants were asked (i) what would help them feel more confident about their career prospects (Fig. 2), (ii) what challenges they face as ECRs (open-ended, not shown), and (iii) which type of activities they were more interested in (Fig.3).

ECRs with different experience levels have different unmet needs.

Figure 2 | ECR needs: number of respondents (%) per experience-level group. A higher number of respondents (red) indicates a greater level of unmet needs within a given category. Needs can score low either because they are less important or the current offer of activities already meets them.

In terms of networking and collaboration-specific activities (Fig. 2, left column), early-stage researchers (0–2 years of experience) expressed a strong need for better access to professional networks, alongside opportunities for interdisciplinary collaborations. For ECRs with 3–5 years and +6 years of experience, opportunities for visiting other labs rank more prominently. This suggests that networking and collaboration remain important across career stages, but the type of support needed changes: earlier-stage ECRs appear to need access to professional networks, while more experienced ECRs place greater emphasis on mobility and collaboration across institutions.

The survey results also point to a strong need for long-term career guidance and planning (Fig. 2, middle), reflecting previous literature that often identifies a lack of this type of support. This need is especially prominent among ECRs with +3 years of experience.

Less experienced ECRs, by contrast, report particularly strong needs for access to experienced mentors, suggesting that mentoring is especially important at the point of entry into the research community. For mid- and later-stage ECRs, the stronger emphasis on career guidance may reflect uncertainty around longer-term progression, independence, and transitions toward more stable roles.

Fig. 2 (right column) reinforces these career-stage differences. Early-stage ECRs report a need for opportunities to develop new skills and competencies, while ECRs with 3–5 and 6+ years place stronger emphasis on project management skills and leadership. This suggests that, as ECRs gain experience, their unmet needs increasingly relate to autonomy and career progression.

Engagement with NGOs and increased visibility of one's own work remain relatively low priorities for all.

Fig. 3 shows preferred activities across two broad areas: professional development and networking (A1), and personal and technical skills development (A2). Developing one's own research project appears among the highest-ranked activities across all career stages, highlighting the importance of research independence throughout the ECR trajectory. Technical skills development is also highly valued by all groups. Among early-stage ECRs, expanding professional networks (A1) and communication skills development (A2) are highly ranked (1st/2nd); for ECRs with 3–5 years, gaining leadership skills (A1) and hands-on research (A2) stand out (ranked 1st/2nd); and among ECRs with +6 years, expanding professional networks and

interdisciplinary collaborations rank similarly high (1st/2nd, A1), as well as hands-on research (A2). Insights into entrepreneurship rank low across all three groups, suggesting limited interest in this type of support among the surveyed ECRs.

Overall, while some valued activities recur across career stages, the support ECRs need differs along the career trajectory. Figs. 2 and 3 highlight stage-specific gaps, and recurring priorities such as developing one's own research project, technical skills, hands-on research, and networking or collaboration. This suggests that support programmes need not offer entirely different activities to each group, but should tailor their purpose, framing, and design to career-stage-specific needs.

Activities such as technical skills development and hands-on research, or developing their own research project and networks, ranked highest in terms of interest.

Figure 3 | Activity interest ranking (in % of respondents) by experience-level group (in years) for professional development and networking activities (from 1st to 7th, top) and personal and technical skills development (from 1st to 6th, bottom).

5. Current landscape of ECR support in EU research projects

Our survey targeting project coordination teams was distributed to over 30 EU-funded research projects, yet fewer than half responded with information on their ECR initiatives. Only a fraction of current EU projects implement dedicated activities for Early Career Researchers, and even fewer have integrated concrete activities into their project design from the proposal stage. This suggests that structured, forward-planned support for ECRs is still far from widespread in EU research projects, and significantly less common than would be desirable. It should, however, be noted that broader project initiatives that particularly benefit ECRs, but were not specifically designed for them, were generally not mentioned in this survey.

We have thus collected details on ECR initiatives from 12 EU research projects in climate science or related fields, with starting and end dates between 2019 and 2028, and coordinated by seven different EU countries: Cyprus, Greece, France, Germany, Spain, Sweden, the UK, and an international entity (United Nations' World Meteorological Organization).

Types of activities offered

Fig. 4 presents the range and frequency of ECR-focused activities reported by EU research projects in our survey. The most commonly implemented activities include networking sessions, conference sessions and social events, each reported by around 50% of the projects. These are followed by webinars, summer schools, and hands-on research opportunities, which were offered by around 25-45% of the projects. A smaller number of projects reported providing technical or communication skills training, as well as career development workshops, mentoring programs, or interdisciplinary collaboration activities.

In addition to the activities shown in the chart, several projects described other valuable forms of ECR engagement, even if these were mentioned

Networking sessions were the most frequently proposed activity.

Figure 4 | Types of activities targeting ECRs proposed by a number of EU research projects. Activities proposed by fewer than two projects are described in the text.

by only one respondent each. These included participation in education and outreach activities, interdisciplinary collaboration efforts, teaching and pedagogical training, and secondments to academic or stakeholder institutions. Other initiatives reflected a more integrated approach, such as assigning central project roles to ECRs, authorship in synthesis papers, and presentations at General Assemblies (GAs). Some projects also implemented embedded mentoring programmes, pairing ECRs with more experienced researchers for career guidance and support. While less systematically reported, these examples point to meaningful ways in which ECRs can be integrated into the life and leadership of EU research projects.

What works (and what does not)

When asked about their most successful activities, several respondents highlighted the value of in-person activities held during GAs, such as career development sessions, networking events, and roundtable discussions. These were considered

successful due to high attendance, informal formats, and opportunities for direct interaction with senior researchers. One project noted that a career development session co-organised with ECRs was particularly effective, citing its participatory nature and alignment with ECR availability. Another project described a communication training, though not originally framed as an ECR-specific initiative, that was especially useful to early-career participants.

Hackathons were mentioned by two projects as having limited success, either due to overly narrow topics or a format that did not align well with ECR needs. One also cited logistical limitations that hindered interaction. One project reported poor outcomes from webinars led by ECRs on their own work, and career development workshops were noted as difficult to be designed effectively in projects involving ECRs with diverse career trajectories, such as those involving both academic and governmental institutions.

Overall, in-person activities were consistently preferred, with all surveyed projects identifying them as the most appealing format for engaging ECRs. Social in-person events, such as informal gatherings and team-building activities, were also frequently highlighted (about 66% of the projects), underscoring the value of fostering connections in relaxed settings. Thematic discussion groups were mentioned by 33% of the projects, suggesting interest in focused peer exchange on specific research topics. In contrast, virtual formats such as webinars and social media groups were rarely cited, each receiving only one mention, further reinforcing the growing sense of “webinar fatigue”. The limited appeal of these formats points to the importance of interaction, spontaneity, and physical presence in successful ECR engagement strategies.

Challenges in developing ECR activities

Figure 5 highlights several recurring challenges faced by EU research projects when developing ECR-focused activities. The two most frequently reported difficulties are identifying the specific needs and interests of ECRs and the limited time or availability of ECRs to participate, each cited by around 58% of the projects. These are followed by issues in designing activities that are both impactful and feasible, as well as organising them with limited resources, both mentioned by around 33% of the projects. Other commonly cited barriers include promoting activities to ensure participation and balancing diverse ECR experience levels. Colleagues have also reported that classing researchers as “early career” actually made them more reluctant to participate in target activities. A few projects reported a lack of engagement from ECRs, without addressing the causes.

In addition to the recurring themes, a few projects highlighted other important barriers. These included the lack of dedicated time slots for ECR activities during GAs, the absence of any ECR planning in the original project proposal, and the limited support or involvement from senior researchers in ECR-focused initiatives. While less frequent, these challenges reinforce the need for early-stage planning, institutional commitment, and a project culture in which senior researchers actively create space, provide mentorship, and share responsibility for implementing meaningful support measures for ECRs.

Together, these insights highlight the need for more intentional planning, resource allocation,

EU projects face multiple challenges in developing activities targeting ECRs

Figure 5 | Challenges faced by a number of EU research projects when developing activities targeting ECRs. Challenges faced by less than two projects are described in the text.

and flexible engagement strategies to effectively support ECRs within EU-funded research projects. Overall, as they reflect qualitative feedback from a

small subset of current EU climate research projects, these conclusions can only be seen as emerging patterns. Further validation would be useful.

These insights highlight the need for more intentional planning, resource allocation, and flexible engagement strategies to effectively support ECRs within EU-funded research projects.

6. The gap: Disconnect between expectations and opportunities

The analysis of both surveys reveals a persistent gap between what ECRs need and expect from EU research projects, and what those projects currently offer.

ECRs are calling for meaningful engagement: opportunities to lead, structured mentorship, tailored career development, and long-term visibility in research planning and output. These expectations vary by experience level but consistently emphasise quality, continuity, and integration, not just participation.

Meanwhile, EU projects tend to offer a limited set of standardised activities — most commonly conference sessions, networking events, webinars, or occasional social events. These are often implemented in an ad-hoc fashion, rarely planned from the proposal stage, and frequently disconnected from the evolving needs of ECRs. More substantive opportunities, such as project leadership roles, mentoring schemes, or career planning support, remain rare.

Many project teams reported a lack of clarity on what ECRs actually need, which makes it difficult

to design effective initiatives. At the same time, they observed limited availability or engagement from ECRs, even when activities were offered. While the reasons for this are not fully captured in our data, one possible explanation is that some ECRs deprioritise these opportunities due to time constraints or competing demands, particularly given the strong focus on research output and funding acquisition in academic evaluation systems. This may discourage participation in activities that, while valuable, are not always seen as essential or rewarded. The result is a self-reinforcing loop: low uptake discourages investment in more ambitious ECR engagement, and the limited offer further reduces perceived relevance.

Ultimately, the gap is not just about what is offered versus what is expected: it reflects a fundamental misalignment in values, incentives, and institutional design. Projects cannot fully support ECRs without addressing this tension, nor can ECRs benefit from available opportunities unless they are better integrated into the structure, timeline, and culture of project work itself.

7. Bridging the gap: Recommendations for EU research projects

Several recent contributions already argue for more intentional, well-resourced support to ECRs. In particular, Pizzolato et al. (2023)¹ call on the European Commission to (i) require capacity-building systems for ECRs, (ii) involve ECRs in decision-making and leadership (e.g., WP co-lead; advisory boards; proposal writing), and (iii) provide bridging resources for career continuity between fixed-term contracts, alongside a community platform that connects ECR expertise with new EU projects. Complementing this EU-level call, a systematic review by Chatzea et al. (2022)⁷ synthesises more than 200 practical tips across five themes: funding/proposal writing, mentorship & networking, visibility, writing/publishing, and personal/professional development. Our recommendations echo these points and translate them into project-level actions.

We outline below a set of concrete recommendations to help bridge the gap between what ECRs expect and what is currently offered in EU-funded research projects. Each recommendation responds directly to survey evidence and is grounded in the principle that effective support must be tailored to the ECR's experience level.

The survey results show that the needs and priorities of ECRs differ with experience, from technical training and basic mentorship at earlier stages to leadership opportunities, grant writing, and continuity support at more advanced stages. Free-text responses describing an "ideal" programme consistently emphasised structured mentoring (e.g., *"Mentoring and Follow-up."*); hands-on grant-writing with feedback (e.g., *"Hands on workshop on proposal writing (and being reviewed)." "A program that helps the ECR with developing their own research career."*); leadership opportunities (e.g., *"Work packages which could be lead and managed by ECRs."*); mobility and cross-lab meet-ups (*"Opportunity for lab visits among partners... two to three times a year."*, *"Funding for exchange visits."*); and

robust technical onboarding (e.g., *"a month-long software training program to ensure standards."*). Several respondents also asked for safer, more inclusive environments (e.g., *"Training on how to deal with abusive power structures."*); protected supervisor time (e.g., *"Clear salary/time allocated to senior researchers to actively support/supervise the ECR's work."*), and a few highlighted exposure to non-academic pathways (policy/industry) and upskilling for jobs outside academia (e.g., *"Upskilling for jobs outside of academia."*).

Table 1 specifies broadly highlighted needs, the most relevant experience-level group for each, the recommended action, feasibility, and an estimate of funding requirements. It aligns with EU-level recommendations (e.g., ECR leadership/decision-making and career-bridging measures) while translating them into stage-specific, project-implementable actions for EU climate research consortia.

The recommendations outlined in the table reflect a clear message from ECRs: support must be relevant, intentional, and responsive to their evolving roles within the research system. Across all these key identified needs, the emphasis falls not only on the type of activity but also on how and when it is implemented. The most effective strategies are those that are planned from the proposal stage, tailored to the experience level of the ECRs involved, and embedded into the daily life of the project.

While not all measures require substantial funding, they do require forethought, coordination, and a cultural shift away from generic or symbolic approaches. The recommendations presented here offer a practical foundation for moving in that direction, and serve as a bridge to the broader question of how EU research projects can foster meaningful, long-term engagement with early-career researchers.

⁷ Chatzea et al. (2022) Recommendations for young researchers on how to better advance their scientific career: A systematic review. *Population Medicine*, 4 (September):1-17.

Table 1 | Summary of recommended actions for EU research projects to meet ECR needs.

ECR Needs	Exp-level group	Recommendation	Feasibility	Funding Needed (per project)
1. Structured mentorship and career guidance	0–2 and 3–5 years	Create a formal, well-resourced mentoring programme involving regular one-to-one sessions, ideally cross-institutional, with a focus on career planning, proposal writing, and transition support. Consider pairing based on goals (e.g. research, policy, teaching). Include mechanisms for follow-up and feedback, and clear salary/time allocated to senior researchers to actively support/supervise the ECRs' work.	Medium	Low – Medium (<5k€ – 30k€)
2. Opportunities to lead and contribute to project decisions	3–5 and 6+ years	Enable ECRs to co-lead tasks or work packages and participate in project proposal development, advisory boards, or strategic meetings. Where feasible, give them ownership over sub-tasks or cross-cutting initiatives. Encourage merit-based leadership regardless of formal status.	High	Low (<5k€)
3. Technical and hands-on skills training	All, especially 0–2 and 3–5 years	Provide targeted, hands-on training in software tools, data analysis, and modelling through workshops, short courses, or summer/winter schools. Include field/lab components where relevant. Consider integrating technical upskilling into onboarding or early project phases.	High	Medium – High (5k€ – > 30k€)
4. Integration with senior researchers	All, especially 3–5 and 6+ years	Avoid isolating ECRs in separate tracks or specific activities: encourage collaboration within broader project structures and activities that include multiple levels of partner research institutes. Design regular, informal formats for interaction with senior researchers, such as mentoring lunches, roundtables, and shared writing or discussion sessions (at family-friendly times).	High	Low (<5k€)
5. Inter-lab mobility and structured exchange opportunities	All, especially 3–5 years	Support short research stays or secondments to other partner institutions. These should be structured, funded, and integrated into the project's work plan. Exchanges should have a clear purpose (e.g. method learning, collaboration building) and support mechanisms (e.g. mentor at host lab).	Medium	Medium – High (5k€ – > 30k€)
6. Support for career continuity and transitions	Mainly 6+ years	Allocate funding for inter-contract bridging periods, enabling senior ECRs to develop proposals, publish, or apply for long-term roles. These periods should be coupled with dedicated mentoring and career coaching. Projects should anticipate and plan for post-project transitions early.	Low – Medium	High (>30k€)

8. Conclusion: Toward meaningful ECR engagement in EU research projects

Our analysis reveals a clear gap between the support Early-Career Researchers expect and what EU-funded research projects currently offer. While many projects include activities for ECRs, these are often generic, underfunded, or added as afterthoughts. At the same time, ECRs themselves face constraints that make it difficult to participate in available initiatives, particularly when those initiatives are poorly timed, disconnected from real career needs, or isolated from the core work of the project.

Despite these challenges, EU research projects are uniquely well-positioned to support ECR career development in ways that go beyond what most institutional environments can offer. Their international, interdisciplinary, and collaborative nature creates opportunities for ECRs to engage across work cultures, research traditions, and experience levels. This is particularly relevant in fast-evolving fields such as climate research, where complexity and cross-border cooperation are inherent to the scientific process. Within these projects, ECRs may gain access to mentors outside their institution, exposure to new perspectives and methods, and early opportunities for international collaboration, all of which are critical for building independent and resilient research careers.

In this context, meaningful ECR engagement should not be a secondary concern: it is central to the sustainability, equity, and innovation potential of the European research landscape. Projects can play an active role in reducing inequalities by giving all ECRs, regardless of background or institutional setting, access to the kinds of support that are essential but unevenly distributed.

Many of the needs identified in our survey can be addressed with relatively low effort, if considered from the start: integrating ECRs into proposal design, assigning leadership roles, embedding mentoring structures, and making space for interdisciplinary exchange. Some changes cost little to nothing, such as inviting ECRs into project-level discussions

or providing them with visibility and recognition. Others require resources and coordination, but the long-term benefits are substantial.

Crucially, our findings show that not all ECRs need the same kind of support. A first-year PhD student has different challenges and expectations than a postdoctoral researcher with over six years of research experience. Senior ECRs, in particular, often lack structured pathways toward independence and long-term stability. Tailoring activities by experience level and providing support to help ECRs navigate the broader research landscape are essential to meet the real complexity of early research careers.

What is the most feasible action EU projects can take now? Start by identifying ECRs in the consortium, inviting them into proposal design and governance, and allocating modest, ring-fenced resources for mentoring, mobility and stage-specific training — then measure uptake and iterate.

And what can funders do in the longer term? Provide incentives, dedicated resources, and recognition for projects that embed meaningful ECR engagement. Promote equity across the research system by ensuring that project participation is not just about producing deliverables, but about supporting the people who make them possible. If prioritised appropriately, ECR support could become a transformative and enduring legacy of collaborative EU research.

